

Specificity of the antiutopia chronotope in trilogy “The Time” by

Yurii Shcherbak¹

Olena Ishchenko

PhD in Philology, Senior Lecturer at the Department of Journalism and Philology,
Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

Larysa Horbolis

Doctor in Philology, Professor at the Department of Ukrainian Language and Literature,
Sumy State Pedagogical University, Sumy, Ukraine

Iryna Zhylenko

Doctor in Philology, Professor, Professor at the Department of Journalism and Philology,
Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

Inna Havryliuk

PhD in Social Communications, Associate Professor of the Department of Journalism and Philology,
Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

Tetiana Kovalova

PhD of Social Communications, Associate Professor, Department of Journalism and Philology,
Sumy State University, Sumy, Ukraine

Received: Jun 14, 2025

Accepted: Jul 12, 2025

Published: Jul 15, 2025

Abstract

The article is devoted to the study of the features of the chronotopic continuum of the antiutopia trilogy “The Time” by Yu. Shcherbak. The research was carried out using general scientific and special literary methods, namely chronotopic analysis, genetic and hermeneutic methods, which allowed us to distinguish traditional and innovative approaches to modeling artistic reality. An interdisciplinary approach was also applied, which, by combining literary studies, philosophy, political science, sociology, cultural studies, and ecology, contributes to a multi-faceted interpretation of the literary text. It was found that the novels “The Smertohryst’s Time”, “Time of the Big Game” and “Time of the Tyrant” are characterized by: a linear narrative “past-present-future”, which moves the narrative from the past to predicting the future; the idea of the cyclicity of the chronotope, which is achieved in the novels with the help of numerous allusions, the introduction of religious images into the plot and direct author’s commentary; artistic modeling of the chronotope of eternity, where all variants of spaces and all times exist simultaneously, which is used to enrich the storyline and help the evolution of the image of the main character of the trilogy, emphasizing his uniqueness and significance for history; an organic combination of internal and external chronotopes, emphasizing the idea of the genetic kinship of man and the environment.

Keywords: artistic space, artistic time, chronotope, problematics, character, novel, antiutopia, literature.

Introduction

From the end of the 19th to the beginning of the 20th century, the problem of chronotope has not lost its relevance and is one of the promising areas of research into literary works. The concept is borrowed from theoretical physics by A. Einstein, from his work “On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies” (1905), where it is stated that the elements of space-time are interconnected and influence each other. When an object moves at a speed close to the speed of light, time slows down

¹In the article, we use the abbreviated name of the works “The Smertohryst’s Time”, “The Time of the Big Game” and “The Time of the Tyrant”, or “The Time” trilogy. The full title is “The Smertohryst’s Time. Mirage of 2077”, “The Time of the Big Game. Phantoms of 2079” and “The Time of the Tyrant. The insight of 2084”.

relative to the observer, and space is compressed (pp. 891-921). In literary-critical discourse, this concept began to be actively used after the 70s of the 20th century. In the *Literary Dictionary-Reference* (1997) edited by R. Hrom'yaka defines an artistic chronotope (Greek "chronos" time and "topos" place) as "the relationship between the temporal and spatial characteristics of the phenomena depicted in a work of art" (2007, p. 714). Yu. Kovaliv in his "Literary Encyclopedia" (2007) provides a definition synthesized from the works of famous scholars, which we will adhere to in this study: "Chronotope is an essential relationship between temporal and spatial connections artistically mastered by literature, with the help of which the genre and genre varieties, the image of a person in literature are determined" (p. 564).

The Polish researcher S. Skwarczynska was the first to study the interaction of temporal and spatial coordinates in a literary text. The first volume of her work "Introduction to Literary Studies" (1954) examined time and space as constructive categories that are of decisive importance for the "literary realization of the presented reality" (Kopystyanska, 2012, p. 47). Analyzing the problems of genealogy, the researcher draws attention to the interaction and interdependence of time/space and literary genre/genre, "because one literary realization of space is provided by a fable, and another by a historical novel" (p. 47). In her theory, artistic space, the boundaries of which can encompass from several countries to one room, is divided into defined (with topographic specificity) and undefined (created by the imagination of the perceiver), closed ("scenery") and open ("landscape"). S. Skwarczynska agrees with the idea of the omnipresence of the category of time and concludes that the temporal flow of a literary work is continuous (a new term "imprint of time" is introduced), even if its image is static and the recipient does not feel the variability. Within the category, the researcher distinguished the time of real reality, the time of the plot, and the time of the representation. The time of real reality is determined by dating, the historical importance of these dates, internal fluidity, etc.

At the beginning of the 21st century, new aspects of the chronotope interpretation appear in literary studies: philosophical, psychological, physical, historical, cognitive, gender, mythological, sociocultural, etc. For example, in the study by A. Temirbolat "Categories of Chronotope and Temporal Rhythm in Literature" (2009), the problem is considered through the prism of synergetics, hermeneutics, communication theory, semiotics, etc. The researcher considers the chronotope to be an integral component of constructing an individual author's picture of the world of the writer, because "it determines the peculiarities of the method, style, and contributes to reflecting the originality of the national thinking of the artist of the word" (p. 4). The work distinguishes social, cultural-historical, fantastic, biological, physical, and mythopoetic chronotope (p. 16). O. Dybovska also distinguishes the following types of chronotope: 1) cyclical – emphasizes the idea of constant repetition and circulation of space and time; 2) linear – expresses the idea of historicism, gradual movement from the past to the present and into the future; 3) chronotope of eternity – creates a space in the artistic world that is in a state when all variants of spaces are simultaneously possible and all times exist; 4) nonlinear – reveals the idea of the multifaceted nature of being (2015, p. 545; 2021, p. 30).

Of particular note is N. Kopystyanska's monograph "Time and Space in the Art of the Word" (2012), which reveals the history of the development and study of these categories in literary studies and related sciences. N. Kopystyanska emphasizes that the term "chronotope" is not identical to the term "spacetime" (after all, the researcher emphasized "the forms of time and chronotope in the novel"), therefore it is appropriate to use it when studying "the organic relationship between time and space, and not just time and space" (p. 53). In our study, we adhere to this position.

Literature Review

At the beginning of the 21st century, one of the most popular literary genres is antiutopia, which is explained by its wide expressive possibilities in modeling artistic reality. The novels of J. Orwell “1984” (1950), H. Wells “The Time Machine” (1992a), “War of the Worlds” (1992b), R. Bradbury “Fahrenheit 451” (1953), K. Vonnegut “Mechanical piano, or Utopia 14” (1969), E. Burgess “1985” (1978) and others have received worldwide recognition. Ukrainian examples of the genre are “Solar Machine” by V. Vynnychenko (2015), “Chronos” by T. Antipovych (2011), “Qin Huan Gong” by H. Tarasyuk (2008) and others. The long evolution of the literary phenomenon, from Antiquity to the present (Ishchenko et al., 2024), has formed established features of such works: the denial of utopian ideas, a wide range of problematic and thematic issues with an emphasis on “eternal” problems, modeling of images of “calmed”, “anxious” and “rebellious” characters, allegoricality, parody, carnivalization, fantastic elements that are intended to increase fear of the future, etc. (Sabat, 2002). But perhaps the most significant genre-defining factors of the antiutopian novel are chronotopic coordinates (Dybovska, 2021), because the plot is built thanks to travel in time and space, and the image of the character is also built thanks to these parameters. The characteristic features of the chronotope of antiutopia are considered to be: a threshold event that divides space-time into the one that existed before it and after it, a separate closed space, the effect of stopping time, the interaction of the external and internal worlds, etc. (Motsna, 2009).

Therefore, the study of the chronotope is one of the most promising areas of literary analysis of a literary text, in particular antiutopia, as evidenced, for example, by the works of O. Dybovska (2015), V. Korkishko (2010), I. Motsna (2009), N. Sherstyuk (2018), etc. Researchers focus on studying the temporal and spatial coordinates of new novels in the antiutopian genre and turn to rereading classical texts in the context of a literary methodology relevant for the beginning of the 21st century. According to M. Kodak, this is “due to the emergence of works of art with increased philosophical content, with in-depth development of oppositions such as ‘up-down’, ‘past-future’, ‘birth-death’, ‘rise-fall’ and numerous intermediate metaphorical paraphrases on motifs designed to show a certain understanding of the spatiotemporal continuum, the extent and continuity of the world” (1988, p. 97). We consider it promising to use chronotopic analysis to study the antiutopian “The Time” trilogy by Yu. Shcherbak, which is a unique phenomenon of contemporary Ukrainian literature, which attracts attention with its original approach to modeling artistic reality and will help determine the principles of constructing spatiotemporal parameters of contemporary antiutopia. The poetics of the trilogy “Time” has already been studied by O. Ishchenko, L. Horbolis, I. Zhylenko and I. Havrylyuk (2024), however, the study of the chronotopic continuum remains a prospect.

Methodology

The complex nature of the study led to the use of general scientific (analysis, synthesis, description) and specific literary methods (chronotopic analysis, genetic and hermeneutic methods). The theory of the chronotope allowed us to analyze the parameters of the artistic world of novels in the harmonious interrelation of temporal and spatial planes, helped to trace their influence on the process of image formation and plot formation. The genetic method contributed to the isolation of the influence of the genre specificity of novels on the artistic modeling of the chronotopic continuum of “The Time” trilogy. The hermeneutic method allowed for a comprehensive interpretation of Yu. Shcherbak’s antiutopias with an emphasis on the chronotope. Also, to understand the specifics of modeling artistic time and space, it is advisable to use an interdisciplinary approach, which allows for a multi-faceted analysis of the text through the prism of philosophy, cultural studies, political science, sociology, psychology, ecology, etc.

Results and Discussion

Chronotope and Geopolitical Reality

It is well known that an important genre-defining dominant of antiutopia is a chronotope that is different from real reality. The authors of such texts artistically model the future and create new spatial coordinates (Sabat, 2002, p. 118). In the “The Time” trilogy, Yu. Shcherbak focused on depicting events in Ukraine and the world in the second half of the 21st century, which is due to the writer’s socio-political activities and his interest in history, politics, geopolitics, processes of state formation, culture and religion, scientific and technological progress, etc. “I seem to have looked into the future, but I do not want my prophecies, God forbid, to come true, because they are about gloomy things. Reflections on what is happening in the world lead to the conclusion that we are standing on the threshold of an era of great uncertainty and major conflicts. Unfortunately, this is how the 21st century is shaping up. Actually, that’s what I’m writing about,” the author notes (2011a, p. 8). Such a creative approach gives literary scholars and critics grounds to debate the genre specificity of the trilogy. For example, K. Rodyk is convinced: “An antiutopia! <...> we don’t have an antiutopia, but prognostic realism. And of the highest standard, because Yurii Shcherbak is an analyst like few others” (2017), that is, he identifies the works as examples of a prognostic novel. The author himself emphasizes: “Let every reader find in my texts what is close to his heart: a political thriller, a love story, a Christian sermon, or descriptions of eighth-generation weapons. To each his own” (2013, p. 8) and defines his texts as examples of an antiutopia and a political novel.

In the first novel, “The Smertohryst’s Time” (2011b), the reader is presented with a geopolitical reality of 2077 that is different from the modern one: the whole world is divided into separate superpowers and political blocs: the Confederation of North American States with its capital in Washington, the Franco-Arab Caliphate in Paris, the Celestial People’s Democratic Empire (on the site of the former China), the Islamic-Mongol Black Horde (which included certain regions of Russia after its disintegration into principalities), and Israel with its capital in Khiva. The competition for world domination and the acquisition of the resources necessary for a full life is being controlled by the Organization of Global Security, which is the bearer of the cultural values of Western civilization and performs the functions of the modern United Nations. The main place of development of the plot is Ukraine, which is ruled by the hetman of the army, General Kuzma-Danylo Makhun, has preserved its independence, but is under threat of destruction by the Black Horde. The capital is divided, like London in its time, by the Dnieper into two parts, East and West Kyiv. On the left bank, immigrants from India and Vietnam live in special ghettos, and on the right bank, next to the government quarters, a special Baty-grad has been built, where a summit is to be held on the inclusion of Ukraine in the Horde as an autonomous part. The main mission of the main character of the trilogy, General of Intelligence Igor Haiduk, who has lived abroad for a long time and feels the consequences of globalization, becomes the awareness of himself as a Ukrainian and the desire to help the country maintain its independence. The threshold event of the first part of the trilogy is the protagonist's return to his homeland (the journey forever changes the character due to movement in space), the restoration of historical memory, which "is a critical element of the formation of the national identity" (Drohomyretska et al., 2024, p. 109), and the subsequent struggle for one's own life among political competitors and the gradual discovery of leadership qualities that help in the fight against the totalitarian regime.

The novels “The Time of the Big Game” (2023) and “The Time of the Tyrant” (2021) are thematic and ideological continuations of “The Smertohryst’s Time”. In the second part of the trilogy, the action takes place in 2079, two years after

the events of the first. Yu. Shcherbak continues the storyline of Igor Haiduk, who lost his memory after the Great Outbreak (a series of nuclear explosions) and gradually remembers the past. He returns to Kyiv and begins to work to restore the state. For Ukraine and the world, this is Zero Time, which, according to the idea, was supposed to be the beginning of a new era, a period that takes into account the mistakes of the past. However, the author emphasizes that humanity has not changed even after the Fourth Global War and the nuclear catastrophe. At the beginning of the novel, the writer describes one of the main places of action, the capital of Ukraine, Kyiv, emphasizing the legacy of the past military confrontation: “Kyiv met Haiduk and his companions with gray twilight, light rain, and defensive structures blocking the Stolychne highway in the area of the Southern Bridge. Haiduk noted that the structures were earthen ramparts rusted from the rain; protective walls made of cracked concrete blocks and heavy, rusted metal structures resembling bridge trusses; barricades made of wet sandbags, entwined with garlands of barbed wire; machine-gun nests and batteries of outdated rocket launchers...” (Shcherbak, 2023, p. 68). It is noteworthy that the writer uses the technique of artistic parallelism, because the path of the character’s self-affirmation as a leader is consonant with the restoration of the artistic space, there is a synchronization of the external and internal chronotope: “On Sunday, February 19, 2079, a warm fog stood over Kyiv and its surroundings, awakening painful memories of spring. And although the sky was still densely covered with clouds, it seemed that the darkness over the earth began to gradually dissipate, losing its absolute power” (2023, p. 104). Other spatial coordinates of the novel are the Suzdal Principality, Switzerland, Turkey, etc.

Religious and Existential Chronotope

One of the genre-defining dominants of the antiutopian novel is an appeal to religious themes or a certain ideological system that prevails in the world or a specific (often fictional) state and replaces religion. Therefore, existential and ontological themes require the author to present his own vision of these issues, in particular the problem of the end of time and space of the visible world, the desire of man to achieve a different, eternal life, that is, to go beyond the boundaries of real time and space. The Ukrainian writer, like H. Wells (1992b) in his time in “The War of the Worlds”, tries to predict the end of earthly history using the example of the civilization of Mars, which died due to weapons that completely destroyed the hydrosphere of the red planet. Despite this, the Earth’s special services are trying to find it and use it for military purposes. The world is threatened by another, rather the last, global catastrophe. This story in the context of the novels acts as a kind of warning for earthlings, expanding the space of the novels to a cosmic scale. According to H. Sabat, this technique is characteristic of this genre: “In antiutopias, the specific place of action can be Germany, England, or the United States. However, most often the boundaries of the spatial scope of the action expand to the limits of the entire earthly world, sometimes the Universe” (2002, p. 126).

After returning to Kyiv, as in the first part of the trilogy, the main character again finds himself in the circle of numerous dangers and political intrigues. Although the confrontation with the Black Horde is over, a new danger awaits the state: the struggle for natural resources. The threshold event in “The Time of the Big Game” is Haiduk’s wounding and meeting with Jesus Christ in a state of clinical death, which takes place outside the chronotopic continuum: “At first, darkness gave way to light, then mountains appeared, and Haiduk joyfully felt the breathlessness of a climber at an altitude of five thousand meters and the blinding cold energy of the peaks, pink and dark purple from the sun. ... He did not notice how the mountains, the abyss, the rocky starting platform disappeared; they stood in the middle of the desert, where heat and thirst tormented Haiduk” (Shcherbak, 2023, pp. 337-338). The author addresses the possibilities of the oneiric and thanatolic chronotope, where “through the creation of a special time-space in which the traditional chronotope is destroyed by the

intertwining in the textual space of elements of the real and the unreal, dream and reality, life and play” (Prylipko, 2007, p. 5). The second and third novels of the trilogy represent two dimensions: historical, which corresponds to the plot line, and timeless, which complements and explains the events, phenomena, actions of the characters, etc. that are real for the novel. The image of Jesus is a traditional cult image for antiutopia, which in the past, thanks to his birth and earthly service, already combined the physical and spiritual worlds.

In the novel by Yu. Shcherbak, the Son of God again crosses the boundary between two worlds, because he cannot simply observe the fateful events of the second half of the 21st century. Such an artistic combination of events that are real for novels and eternity creates the illusion of the repetition of biblical events and emphasizes the idea of the cyclical nature of Earth’s history: “He stood on the top of the Mount of Olives and wept: before Him on the hills spread Jerusalem - dead, gray, like the body of the deceased Lazarus, a city destroyed by the blows of nuclear warheads: the stones, once alive - white, opal, pink, which at dawn shone in the rays of the sun, which rose behind the Mount of Olives over the Judean desert and delighted the heart of Christ in His earthly life, - turned into dead limestone, burned by hellish fire and poisoned by radiation... Now Jesus was met by dead silence. No traces of the Temple on Mount Moriah remained, just as the building of the Mosque of Omar was absent... Having descended down the stone drainpipe, to where he hoped to see the remains of the Wailing Wall, Christ wandered for a long time in the labyrinth of ruins, not recognizing his favorite places” (Shcherbak, 2023, pp. 334-335). The meeting and dialogue with Jesus is important for the self-identification of Iror Haiduk. From the beginning of the trilogy until this episode, the character periodically reflects on the meaning of religion in a person’s life. For example, in “The Smertohryst’s Time”, he admits that he does not consider himself a believer. As the plot unfolds, Haiduk gradually realizes the significance of the figure of Jesus Christ in world history, in the life of each individual person, and in his own as well, which makes his spiritual growth and personal encounter with the Son of God possible. He brings the protagonist back to life and makes him realize that his life mission – to help Ukraine stand firm amidst geopolitical threats and unite the Eastern and Western parts of Christianity – has not yet been fulfilled. To emphasize the effect of the character’s exit from the historical chronotope, the author describes the moment of awakening as follows: “...Not understanding anything – where is he? who is he? and what happened to him? – Haiduk opened his eyes: the room was shining with unbridled sunlight <...> Only on the fifth day <...> did he finally come to his senses, asking Olya if Easter would be celebrated soon, because he so wanted to taste a sweet Paska with raisins. He was very surprised to learn that Easter had long passed, leaving a noticeable mark in the history of mankind: it was on Sunday, April 23, 2079, that the Time of Great Darkness ended” (2023, pp. 341-342). So, the protagonist was unconscious for a month, although it seemed to him that he had been in this state for several days.

Chronocollapse and Character Development

The third novel in the trilogy “The Time of the Tyrant” continues the storyline of the previous two, focusing on the artistic modeling of the events of 2084 in Ukraine, Italy (Vatican), the Confederation of North American States, the Middle and Far East, etc. Ihor Haiduk becomes the Coordinator of the military regime in Ukraine, which is rapidly developing after overcoming the legacy of nuclear winter. The threshold event in this novel is the “insight” of the main character on how to overcome negative qualities in himself (rage, ruthlessness, cruelty, the need to give up many things or people for the common good, etc.), which is generated by unlimited power. He realized that he did not want to become a real tyrant who is capable of anything in order to maintain power: “I said goodbye forever to the naive myth of “my team”, “my people”, “guys who can be trusted”. The teacher was right: the path up, to the heights of power, is not a hike of climbers in a group to

Everest. It is a journey of self-denial and fierce stratospheric loneliness, when no one can be trusted, when the soul is scorched, as if a battlefield were napalm” (Shcherbak, 2021, p. 182). Haiduk finds the strength to renounce power, and therefore defeats the system and finds peace of mind together with his son and, in the future, with the woman he loves.

Another example of the relationship between the main and secondary images and the chronotope in the trilogy by Yu. Shcherbak is the correlation of the feelings and consciousness of the characters with temporal and spatial concepts. Thus, the feeling of spiritual emptiness is compared with the stopping of historical time and disorientation in space. The author calls this state the concept of chronocollapse, temporal and spatial confinement. In the minds of the characters, “there are no external signs of a change in time – the change of daylight to night, no orders to sleep or get up in the morning. No one responded to Haiduk’s knock on the iron door painted with green “tank” paint and his demands to provide him with a lawyer, and soon Haiduk lost his sense of time, fell into the trap of chronocollapse...” (Shcherbak, 2011). The same thing happens with other characters. For example, one of Haiduk’s friends, Bozhena, talks about her stay in the ZEK: “I had the impression that time had stopped, that I was living in the thirteenth century on a farm forgotten by everyone, and horsemen in black were galloping past this farm – crusaders, or something, somewhere far away cities were burning, battles were raging, and you were sitting and doing nothing, not knowing, not understanding. ... It’s strange, but when I was on Mars, sitting for a year at our base, I had the same feeling: chronocollapse” (Shcherbak, 2011). ZEKs are an antiutopian parody (which is emphasized by the name ZEK from “zakluchenny”) of a Ukrainian national society with an ideal structure amidst global political chaos: Ukrainian language, national clothes, dishes, traditions. But in its essence it is a kind of reservation (even the name contains undisguised irony), where ethnic Ukrainians live, from whom a person may no longer go out into the big world. Residents speak in whispers, fear persecution, television and newspapers are banned, that is, it is a physically and psychologically closed chronotope. “The Great Outbreak forever incinerated or mutilated the memory of humanity – storage facilities with electronic information carriers, libraries and cinematheques, as well as such material creations as skyscrapers, bridges, metallurgical and oil refineries, enterprises of the pharmacological and bioengineering industries, gas storage facilities, nuclear and thermal power plants, gas stations, hypermarkets and wholesale warehouses, entertainment centers. And the Earth became empty and void, and Darkness fell into the abyss. ... Time foamed. The old time burned in the flames of the Great Outbreak, and the new one has not yet begun. And the great Timelessness came to Earth, the Zero cycle, absolute Zero” (Shcherbak, 2023, p. 17). It is noteworthy that after a series of explosions, Haiduk lost his memory and it took him time, about two years, to find himself. With the return of memories, the process of rethinking the past and values that motivated him for a long time is activated. The character focuses on the essence of the concept of “Homeland” and concludes that for a long time he was guided by false ideas, phantoms that only misled him and forced him to waste his energy on unessential things. He realizes: Homeland is “the place where you were born – your home, a quiet Kyiv courtyard, an always tired father, a mother who loved you above all else” (p. 17), and he becomes determined to participate in the restoration of Ukraine.

In “The Time” trilogy Yu. Shcherbak repeatedly uses the technique typical of antiutopias of involving symbolic details in the text, which are markers of different eras and cultures, thanks to which spatial and “temporal layers <...> intersect, coincide, overlap, different time periods exist in parallel” (Sabat, 2002, p. 29). In one sentence or paragraph, a synthesis of historical realities of different cultures and eras is created, the names of famous figures are mentioned, which are separated by years, centuries, or even millennia. Thus, a kind of historical mosaic arises in the work: “In front of the Basmanov Palace – a gigantic forty-five-story building with columns, towers, and spires in the style of Moscow high-rise buildings of the

1950s – we saw a monument to Ivan the Terrible. The monument was postmodern... the tsar in the Monomakh cap. <...> And only the wolves that surrounded the sovereign and the blockhouse in a ring, with their heads raised, were ominously gray, the color of soldiers' greatcoats. <...> 'Isn't this a dream? - thought Haiduk - Was I recently in Washington, where white-pink sakura blooms?'" (Shcherbak, 2011). In addition to allusions, "The Time" trilogy contains facts about historical periods and events that were crucial for the fate of humanity: "When asked by Rosyak about the attitude of his Ukrainian colleagues to the OGB proposal to introduce Polish troops into Western Ukraine, Pryadko replied that this was a matter for the political leadership of the state. Haiduk said that a certain analogy could arise with Stalin's proposal in 1939 to introduce the Red Army into the territory of Poland in order to deter Germany: the reaction of the Polish leadership at that time was sharply negative" (Shcherbak, 2011). These excursions into the past help the author explain the current course of events and warn against their repetition in the future.

Conclusions

To reveal the multidimensionality of the chronotope in the trilogy by Yu. Shcherbak, an interdisciplinary approach was used, which revealed its philosophical and political depth and aesthetic complexity. The achievements of philosophy and cultural studies were used to understand time as a metaphysical category (apocalypticism, crisis of values, the end of history) and space as a symbol of a dystopian future, in which the fear of dehumanization is embodied (the concept of "catastrophic time" as a reflection of the philosophical and cultural anxieties of the era). Through the prism of sociology and political science, the chronotope was interpreted in the context of political threats (dictatorship, biotechno-tyranny, war, nuclear war, etc.) and the presentation of time and space as a reflection of total control, information surveillance, isolation. The basics of ecology contributed to the analysis of the catastrophic chronotope associated with the degradation of nature under the influence of human activity, ecological apocalypse (images of contaminated zones, "dead cities", changes in the biosphere as an artistic prediction). The psychoanalytic approach contributed to the consideration of the chronotope as a reflection of the collective unconscious, fears of the future, and the traumatic experience of the character.

Yu. Shcherbak does not depart from the world and domestic tradition of constructing the chronotope of an antiutopian novel, artistically modeling several models of the spatiotemporal continuum that complement each other. First, the linear narrative "past-present-future" is the embodiment of the idea of historicism: imitation, continuation, development of the achievements of the past to improve the future. Second, in "The Time" trilogy, the writer defends the idea of the cyclicity of the chronotope, which is achieved in the novels with the help of numerous allusions, the introduction of religious images into the plot, and direct authorial commentary. Third, the novels trace the chronotope of eternity, where all variants of spaces and all times exist simultaneously, which is used to enrich the storyline and helps the evolution of the image of the main character of the trilogy, emphasizing his uniqueness and significance for history. Fourth, "The Time" trilogy is notable for its organic combination of internal and external chronotopes, which emphasizes the idea of the genetic kinship between man and the environment. Having analyzed the chronotopic continuum of the trilogy, we can assert that Yu. Shcherbak, relying on the world literary tradition, actively uses the rules of constructing a chronotope characteristic of antiutopia: 1) each novel has a threshold event that divides the diegesis into "before" and "after" (changes in the life of the main character caused by local and global factors); 2) the effect of stopping time (chronocollapse), which is used to reflect the internal state (spiritual emptiness, confusion, disorientation) of the characters; 3) the closedness of space, which emphasizes the limitations of the characters, not the ability to be truly free. The author also showed an original approach, because he did

not depict fictional countries, but tried, relying on his political experience, to predict the prospects for the development of the real world in the future.

The categories of space and time in “The Time” trilogy have a symbolic meaning, filling the artistic fabric of the works with deep philosophical content, which encourages the recipient to develop critical thinking, rethink historical events, and encourage reflection on current and “eternal” issues.

Future research could explore the reception of Shcherbak's chronotopic vision by different cultural groups or compare his use of the chronotope with that of other contemporary anti-utopian writers.

Bibliographic references

1. Antipovych, T. (2011). *Chronos*. Kyiv: A-BA-BAGA-LA-MA-GA, 200 p.
https://shron1.chtyvo.org.ua/Antypovych_Taras/Khronos.pdf
2. Bradbury, R. (1953). *Fahrenheit 451*. Anniversary Edition. <https://anylang.net/en/books/en/fahrenheit-451>
3. Burgess, A. (1978). 1985. Filibusta. URL: <http://flibusta.site/b/412840/read>
4. Drohomiretska, L., Yuhan, N., Kostyuchok, P., Babenko, L., & Kurok, O. (2024). The influence of historical memory on the formation of national identity: a response to the challenges of the Russian-Ukrainian war. *Amazonia Investiga*, 13(81), 108-116. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2024.81.09.8>
5. Dybovska, O. (2015). Artistic time-space of Valery Shevchuk's fairy tales. *Prykarpatskyi visnyk NTSh. Slovo*. No. 2 (30). P. 543-550.
https://www.academia.edu/30105550/%D0%A5%D0%A3%D0%94%D0%9E%D0%96%D0%9D%D0%86%D0%99_%D0%A7%D0%90%D0%A1%D0%9E%D0%9F%D0%A0%D0%9E%D0%A1%D0%A2%D0%86%D0%A0_%D0%9A%D0%90%D0%97%D0%9E%D0%9A_%D0%92%D0%90%D0%9B%D0%95%D0%A0%D0%86%D0%AF_%D0%A8%D0%95%D0%92%D0%A7%D0%A3%D0%9A%D0%90_.pdf
6. Dybovska, O. (2021). *Ukrainian literary fairy tale of the late 20th - early 21st centuries: poetics of the chronotope*. Bachelor's thesis, Kolomyia Institute of the State Institution of Higher Education "Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University" https://uacademic.info/ua/document/0421U102382#google_vignette
7. Einstein, A. (1905). *On the Electrodynamics of Moving Bodies*. *Annalen der physik*, 17(10), 891-921.
<https://users.physics.ox.ac.uk/~rtaylor/teaching/specrel.pdf>
8. Ishchenko, O., Horbolis, L., Bondarenko, O., Zhylenko, I., & Havryliuk, I. (2024). Features of the poetics of contemporary antiutopia (based on the of the trilogy “The Time” by Yuri Shcherbak). *Amazonia Investiga*, 13(80), 122-130. <https://doi.org/10.34069/AI/2024.80.08.11>

9. Kodak, M. (1988). *Poetics as a System: Literary-Critical Essays*. Kyiv: Dnipro. 159 p. <https://franko.libs.net.ua/cgi-bin/koha/opac-detail.pl?biblionumber=119756>
10. Kopystyanska N. (2012). *Time and Space in the Art of the Word: Monograph*. Lviv: PAIS. 344 p. <https://book-ye.com.ua/catalog/literaturoznavstvo/chas-i-prostir-u-mystetstvi-slova/>
11. Korkishko, V. (2010). Space-time as a form-forming category of a literary text. *Current problems of Slavic philology*. Issue XXIII. Part 1. P. 388-395. <http://dspace.nbuv.gov.ua/bitstream/handle/123456789/17235/45-Korkishko.pdf?sequence=1>
12. Hrom'yaka, R. T. (Ed.). (2007). *Literary dictionary-directory* (2nd ed., corrected and supplemented, p. 751). Kyiv: Academy, 751 p. https://shron1.chtyvo.org.ua/Hromiak_Roman/Literaturoznachnyi_slovyk-dovidnyk.pdf
13. Kovaliv, Yu. (2007). *Literary Encyclopedia. In 2 volumes*. Vol. 2. Kyiv: Academic Center "Academy". 624 p.
14. Motsna, I. (2009). Time and Space in the Anti-Utopian Novels of Boryslav Pekich. *Comparative Studies of Slavic Languages and Literatures. In Memory of Academician Leonid Bulakhovsky*. Issue 10. Pp. 360-369. http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/kdsm_2009_10_59
15. Orwell, G. (1950). *1984*. A Signet Book the New American Library. <https://archive.org/details/dli.ernet.240835/page/1/mode/2up>
16. Prylipko, I. (2007). *System-forming models of ideography by Valery Shevchuk*. 15 p. <https://mydisser.com/en/avtoref/view/sistemotvorchi-modeli-idiografii-valeriya-shevchuka.html>
17. Rodyk K. (2017). *Between utopia and anti-: review of Yuriy Shcherbak's book "The Smertohryst's Time"*. Bukvoid. <https://web.archive.org/web/20210714114101/http://bukvoid.com.ua/digest/2017/08/30/101632.html>
18. Sabat, H. (2002). *In the labyrinths of utopia and antiutopia*. Drohobych: Kolo, 160 p. (In Ukrainian).
19. Shcherbak, Yu. (2013). The smertohrysts and the "after-future". *Literary Ukraine*. No. 12. March 21. P. 8.
20. Shcherbak, Yu. (2011a). People without morals are smertohrysts. *Ukrainian literary newspaper*. No. 10. P. 8.
21. Shcherbak, Yu. (2011b). *The Smertohryst's Time. Mirage of 2077*. URL: <https://knigoed.club/1293-chas-smertohristiv-mirazhi-2077-jurij-mikolajovich-shherbak.html>
22. Shcherbak, Yu. (2023b). *The Time of the Great Game. Phantoms of 2079*. 2 ed. Kyiv, 544 p. https://chtyvo.org.ua/authors/Scherbak_Yurii/Chas_velykoi_hry_Fantomy_2079_roku/
23. Shcherbak, Yu. (2021). *The Time of the Tyrant. The Epiphany of 2084*. Kyiv, 544 p. https://chtyvo.org.ua/authors/Scherbak_Yurii/Chas_tyrana_Prozrinnia_2084_roku/
24. Sherstyuk, N. (2018). Chronotope as a literary category of genesis, evolution, discourse. *Philological Sciences*. No. 28. P. 56-61. <http://dspace.pnpu.edu.ua/bitstream/123456789/11674/1/Sherstiuk.pdf>
25. Tarasyuk, G. (2008). *Qin Huan Gong*. Brovary: "Culture", 356 p. URL: https://shron1.chtyvo.org.ua/Tarasiuk/Tsin_Huan_Gon.pdf?

26. Temirbolat, A. (2009). *Categories of chronotope and temporal rhythm in literature*. Monograph. 504 p. <https://i.twirpx.link/file/1757811/>
27. Vonnegut Jr., K. (1969). *Player Piano*. Avon Press, 398 p. <https://antilogicalism.com/wp-content/uploads/2017/07/player-piano.pdf>
28. Vynnychenko, V. (2015). *The Solar Machine*. Ridley. <https://readli.net/chitat-online/?b=165601&pg=1>
29. Wells, H. G. (1992a). *The Time Machine*. E-Book #35. Gutenberg Ebook <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/35/35-h/35-h.htm>
30. Wells, H. G. (1992b). *The War of the Worlds*. Gutenberg Ebook. <https://www.gutenberg.org/files/36/36-h/36-h.htm>